

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

Deliverable

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Dissemination and Outreach no1**

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Disclaimer

RAMONES is a European Innovation Council (EIC) FET Proactive project in the Environmental Intelligence Scope B, related to radically novel approaches to resilient, reliable and environmentally responsible in-situ monitoring. It is funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 FET proactive programme, via grant agreement No. 101017808.

RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity gap in sampling needs and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. These goals will be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy. It will also design new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
EIC	European Innovation Council
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
FET	Future and Emerging Technologies
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
RI	Research Infrastructure
SoA	State of the Art
WP	Work Package
WWW	World Wide Web

Table of Contents

1. Introduction to Dissemination, Outreach and Communication Material	9
1.1 Context	9
1.2 Structure of the document	9
1.3 Objectives and approach	10
2. Material's target group/audience	12
3. Dissemination material	13
3.1 Project identity Banners and posters	14
3.2 Leaflets	17
3.3 Pens and pencils	18
3.4 Notebooks	19
3.5 Folders A4	19
3.6 Badges and ribbons	20
3.7 Personalized business cards	21
3.8 Antistress balls	22
3.9 Coffee/tea mugs	22
3.10 T-shirts	23
3.11 Additional material	24
4. Conclusion	24

Abstract

RAMONES is an ambitious, high-risk project which aims to prove that innovative combination and advancement of recent developments in detector technology and sensor materials, low-power-autonomous robotic systems, and process-modelling theories, have the potential to overcome contemporary limitations and open the window to high temporal and spatial resolution underwater radioactivity measurements, in situ and in near real time, forming a game changer in deep-water environmental monitoring. RAMONES proposes a new generation of submarine radiation-sensing instruments, assisted by State of the Art (SoA) robotic and artificial intelligence (AI) solutions towards understanding radiation related risks near and far from coastal areas, while providing data for the international community towards shaping new policies and governance guidelines for environmental sustainability, economic growth and human health. RAMONES will provide tools for long-term, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, propose new AI-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these can be achieved by combining SoA equipment from various disciplines in well-balanced synergy, and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. Additionally, one of the main goals is to introduce novel ways of monitoring and response channels to inform key socio-political stakeholders at regular intervals from medium (daily, weekly) to low (monthly to inter-annually) frequencies.

An additional key task of the project is to increase local citizens, as well as stakeholders and policymakers' awareness and involvement based on diverse dissemination, communication and outreach activities, through scientific evidence and FAIR data principles. RAMONES is adopting several intense dissemination and communication strategies towards raising public awareness and attracting citizen involvement through multiple identified channels and target groups.

The main aim of this deliverable is to provide the details of various promotional materials to achieve the "Awareness, Communication, Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement and Exploitation" goals. We aim to clearly define a RAMONES branding scheme and disseminate the project's objectives by investing on visual promotion of the project's logo, website, social media, but also retain the association of people using the materials with the project.

1. Introduction to Dissemination, Outreach and Communication Materials

1.1 Context

This document is part of Work Package 5 (WP5, *Citizen Awareness, Communication and Dissemination Activities*), and in particular of Task T5.3 on Raising Citizens Awareness, Dissemination, Communication and Outreach activities.

The document outlines the vision, strategy and a specific plan of opportunities offered to expand the baseline dissemination of the RAMONES project via related materials.

This plan lays out the roadmap to maximize the output from the project effort in the direction of:

- (i) bringing its results to the wider and most appropriate audience that will be interested or motivated in exploiting or uptaking it, and
- (ii) create a minimal, but effective, visual representation of the project and communicate it to stakeholders and the public.

According to the EU definition, outreach activities are expected to engage a large audience. Our goal is to promote the research project, raise public and industry interest and maximize the dissemination impact via various communication channels. At the same time, RAMONES brand name can be founded, strengthened and grown. In line with the above, designing, creating and sharing RAMONES material is expected to serve these goals.

1.2 Structure of the document

The current document is organized according to the following structure and contents:

1. **Objectives and approach:** Introduction to the objectives to raise awareness, communication, dissemination and outreach and the relevant approaches for consequent development.
2. **Material's target group/audience.** The dissemination material is distributed to various target audiences (in research, business and technology) during various events defined in the corresponding section of the document.
3. **Dissemination Material.** Finally, the hardcopy, materials and gadgets are described in detail.

1.3 Objectives and approach

The objectives of the RAMONES citizen awareness, communication, dissemination and outreach and how they will be implemented are described in the following table:

Table 1. Communication, Dissemination, Citizen Awareness, Outreach, Engagement and Exploitation Plan approach.

Type of Activity	RAMONES Objectives	Means and Activities
Communication	1. Increase RAMONES visibility in terms of activities and outcomes; receive valuable feedback	Communication effort aiming at the targeted multiple audience beyond RAMONES community; Exploit feedback strengthening potentials and exploitation
	2. Inform Society and communities / enhance the engagement with stakeholders	Communicate project outcomes to a broad, diverse audience. Targeted communication efforts towards target groups (radioactivity, environmental, marine robotics, social scientists, analysts) and relevant stakeholders.
Dissemination	3. Position RAMONES as a top-rank EIC project and in Environmental Intelligence European projects ecosystem	Intensive dissemination activities are linked to the offered project outcomes to promote them during their operational phase within the considered sectors and the Environmental Intelligence community.
	4. Boost networking and engagement strategy of the RAMONES results	Targeted and synchronized dissemination, communication, exploitation and communities' engagement activities aimed at all target audiences and policymakers.
Raise Awareness	5. Share knowledge of the offered methodologies and instrumentation	Project development along with communication and dissemination activities and targeted communities' engagement aiming at primary target audiences.
	6. Raise awareness and demonstrate how RAMONES outcomes (methodologies and instrumentation) can cater to the needs of the stakeholders and the communities	Communication efforts along with carefully designed activities for maximizing impact including hands-on training of several primary targeted audiences.

Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no1

Outreach	7. Engage large audiences and bring knowledge and expertise from RAMONES objectives and outcomes to the relevant communities, policy makers and stakeholders, as well as the general public.	Outreach activities will be accomplished via approaches specialized to audiences in question, such as workshops, conferences, webinars, datathons/hackathons always with the appropriate communication material
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In particular, the main objectives are:

- to establish a visual and textually recognizable impression of the project and its work.
- to maximize the impactful visibility of the project's work and achievements.
- to engage stakeholders that can support project sustainability through both update and feedback and can further empower the vision around EIC and Environmental Intelligence goals.
- to provide essential information and knowledge on the RAMONES project to third parties focusing especially on the H2020 and Environmental Intelligence landscape.

The approach can be summarized under the following seven (7) conditions:

- **Announce RAMONES to the scientific community:** actions are required to properly explain the RAMONES's vision and strategy, identify key target groups (targeted interest groups in research, business and technology) and define contents and channels for each target.
- **Partners: the first believers, first users and first promoters.** It is necessary to gain the engagement of the partners (by means of internal communication) and to take advantage of each partner's knowledge and contacts to boost their best contributions. A recurrent task of enhancing and sharing synergies will drive the best achievements.
- **Understand the real needs of the target groups (Research groups, RIs stakeholders, scientific groups, technology providers, policy makers/stakeholders, general public):** to achieve a deep understanding of real needs it is necessary to enable and promote 2-way communication channels.
- **Tune the offer:** to define values, services and solutions, we need to transfer to the communities, stakeholders and wide public the identified needs.

- **Boost the demand:** By means of close access to research, public communities and stakeholder needs, identification of the communication messages, and dissemination of content and benefits of RAMONES outcomes
- **Knowledge hub:** Content and knowledge repository implies coordination of any news and contents among project partners, and their later dissemination and storage.
- **Measurement & Control:** No achievement can be made without its measurement and control, both for reporting purposes and for best possible results tactics in order to strengthen the recurrent collaboration among all the partners.

2. Material's target group/audience

To achieve dissemination of RAMONES's aims and broadening out communication with the public, the material that has been designed targets various audiences, such as:

- researchers
- funders
- industry parties
- policy makers
- stakeholders
- general public including journalists, students, innovators, startups, NGOs, or the society in a broader sense.

The dissemination material will be also shared within all the project partners.

The hardcopy material will be deployed for wide use in face-to-face meetings and events, conferences, public and targeted workshops, summer schools, training and outreach events and also during fairs and exhibitions thus helping to consolidate the RAMONES brand. All these events aim to bring together the above-mentioned audiences to exchange knowledge and information, generate opportunities for collaboration, and disseminate project activities (from research, business or technology).

3. Dissemination material

Hard-copy materials and gadgets, in the form of memorabilia, are types of dissemination material that the project is engaged to create according to its needs, in order to achieve the project communication objectives, strengthen project's identification, consolidate engagement and arouse the interest of the project among a varied public.

The project identity is characterized by a particular brand image style with a unique color palette (black-blue-green-yellow-grey-white) and typography (Roboto, Arial). These are applied in any document (leaflets, brochures, etc.) and other branding material.

In addition, any product or reusable material related to the RAMONES project (posters, leaflets, banners, notebooks, pens, etc.) is and will be designed incorporating the logo and RAMONES patterns.

The dissemination material comprises the following:

- project identity banners / posters
- leaflets
- notebooks
- pens and pencils
- folders A4
- badges and ribbons
- antistress balls
- personalized business cards
- stickers
- buttons
- mugs
- t-shirts

Some examples of the hardcopy that are produced, such as notebooks, folders, cards, pen, pencils and buttons are shown in Figure 1.

Unfortunately, the impact of the global COVID-19 pandemic limits the distribution of the material at this point, with digital documents being the main dissemination and promotion tool.

Nevertheless, all the dissemination materials are available on the project's common Cloud drive and are offered on the website for public use.

Figure 1. RAMONES samples of dissemination material.

The hardcopy, materials and gadgets are described in some detail below:

3.1 Project identity Banners and posters

Any general-purpose document (such as banners, posters, etc.) involves content related to the project's scope and research already been done (scientific publications/presentations) and may also include contents coming from other contributions to the RAMONES scope (for instance, deliverables or specific developments) or may be specifically developed for a specific target (for instance, the promotion of an event).

The project identity banners of RAMONES demonstrate the ambition and the objectives of the project. On the banner the following are also presented: the Consortium: the contact information, the social media accounts, the EU logo and an illustration showing the instruments that will be used in the project.

Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no1

RAMONES

RAMONES ambition is to bring together innovative technology and recent advancements in sensory materials, low-power autonomous robotic systems, and state-of-the-art modelling techniques to overcome current limitations in performing in situ and in near-real time underwater radioactivity measurements at large spatiotemporal scales.

Objectives

- 1 Design, develop and validate novel instrumentation towards a holistic marine radioactivity detection and monitoring.
- 2 Design, develop, and validate the efficacy of multiple cooperative robotic systems endowed with self-deployment and self-awareness capabilities and equipped with new marine radiometry instrumentation to adaptively monitor radioactivity levels of extended volumes of the ocean.
- 3 Design and implement intensive integration and adequate validation activities in a step-wise approach to provide reliable data, form policies and strengthen the resilience of EU coastal communities and ecosystems.
- 4 Design and develop novel methods and algorithms for data calibration/rectification, multi-modal data analytics for information extraction, as well as modelling for critical environmental monitoring tasks.
- 5 Establish a visual and textual identity of the project and its work and maximise the impactful visibility of project's work and achievements relying on Open Access and FAIR principles.
- 6 Design a new blueprint for Environmental Intelligence in EU.

Consortium

National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Institute for Systems and Robotics, EvoLogics, ENS, PSL, National Technical University of Athens, PLOATECH, Durham University, LPC

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Figure 2. RAMONES banner.

Figure 3. RAMONES banner presented in the 29th Symposium of the Hellenic Nuclear Physics Society on September 24th and 25th 2021.

Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no1

3.2 Leaflets

The content of the leaflets is relevant to RAMONES goals, services and benefits. These brochures are threefold and presenting:

- the cover page with the RAMONES logo in blue background and the color bar
- the inner pages with the ambition and the 5 objectives of the project, together with a map showing the Mediterranean area and two pictures of the instruments that will be used in the project
- the back cover with the Consortium, the Coordinator's information, the social media accounts and the EU logo with the text referring to the funding

These documents are designed for a general audience and will be downloadable from the web site.

Figure 4. RAMONES leaflet.

Figure 5. RAMONES leaflet printed version.

3.3 Pens and pencils

The pens and pencils are designed incorporating the RAMONES logo. An example of this branding material in black color is shown below.

Figure 6. RAMONES pen and pencil.

3.4 Notebooks

The A4 size notebooks are in portrait format, with white background and the logo of RAMONES printed on them. The discrete color bar is printed at the bottom of each page. Two options of notebook styles are available, option A and option B, as presented in Figure 6. The notebook is ideal for taking notes and project planning.

Figure 7. RAMONES notebook.

3.5 Folders A4

The RAMONES folders have A4 size (Fig. 7), which is considered the most convenient size for keeping together leaflets and notes from the RAMONES A4 notebook. The prominent color of the A4 folder is blue. When open, in the front page of the folder the RAMONES logo is printed

in the middle of the page, but in the back page the logo is smaller and printed on the bottom left corner together with the webpage link. On the bottom right corner the EU logo and the text referring to the funding are printed. Also, at the bottom of both pages is the distinctive color bar.

Figure 8. RAMONES folder A4.

3.6 Badges and ribbons

The badge and ribbon style follows the color palette of RAMONES dissemination material. The size of the badges is 7x10 cm and there are two color options, A and B. The name on the badge is modifiable and can be easily changed and printed (see Fig. 8).

Option A

Option B

Figure 9. Example of RAMONES badges (Options A and B).

3.7 Personalized business cards

The RAMONES personalized business cards can be distributed to a target audience during various events to communicate and promote the project as well as the basic information of each party. The size of the cards is 8.5x5.5 cm and are double-sided, where on one side the logo of RAMONES in blue background is depicted and on the other side the logo, the color bar, the name and personal information of the card owner are printed in white background. See Figure 9 for a printed sample.

Figure 10. Example of RAMONES personalized cards.

3.8 Antistress balls

Antistress balls are excellent tools to relieve stress and release anxiety, especially during long working hours in the office. They also improve motor skills, loosen muscles and promote blood pressure. The antistress balls are printed with the RAMONES logo to advertise our brand.

Figure 11. RAMONES antistress ball (front and back sides).

3.9 Coffee/Tea Mugs

Two colors, white and black, were selected for the mugs to present the RAMONES design.

Figure 12. RAMONES mugs in white and black color.

3.10 T-shirts

The production of communication material also includes t-shirts that follow the design of the RAMONES project. There are two options, a black or white background with the characteristic logo printed on them.

Figure 13. RAMONES t-shirts in black and white color.

3.11 Additional material

Additional dissemination material may include:

- stickers
- buttons
- anti COVID-19 masks
- material to target special events

4. Conclusion

With the present Deliverable, we highlight the importance of the RAMONES brand by producing a collection of various types of promotional materials, which will support the dissemination and outreach objectives as they have been set early in the project's timeline. The high quality, the variety, the visible brand name and the wide targeted audience supports the RAMONES vision for communicating the scope, the objectives and the results to all potential stakeholders in research, technological and social sectors.